

The Clovis Temporal Barrier. Discussions about its current relevance

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Abstract: Towards the first half of the 20th century, there was a boom of the interest of learning about the origin of American man, due to the findings in the southern United States, which were the basis for the typologies and lithic industries of the Clovis and Folsom types, taking them as the oldest evidence on the continent, used in the same way as a wall with which each new finding to which a corresponding or higher age was attributed should be compared, denigrating almost all those who were supposedly older, however the new evidence, and the discoveries of the last 40 years, debates about the current functionality of the Clovis model (Late Entry to the American continent), have resulted in the proliferation of other models more in line with the current evidence, which has shaken the Clovis Barrier.

Keywords: *Late Entry Model, Early Entry Model and Pre-Clovis.*

Resumen: Hacia la primera mitad del siglo XX, se produjo un boom, en cuanto al interés para conocer sobre el origen del hombre Americano, debido a los hallazgos en el sur de los Estados Unidos, los cuales fueron las bases para las tipologías e industrias líticas de los tipos Clovis y Folsom, tomándolos como las evidencias con mayor antigüedad en el continente, usados de igual forma como un muro con el que se debía comparar cada Nuevo hallazgo al que se le atribuyera una edad correspondiente o superior, denigrando a casi todos aquellos que tuvieran una supuesta antigüedad mayor, sin embargo las nuevas evidencias, y a los descubrimientos de los últimos 40 años, los debates sobre la funcionalidad actual del modelo Clovis (Entrada Tardía al continente Americano), han dado como resultado la proliferación de otros modelos más acordes con la evidencia actual, los cuales han puesto a temblar a la Barrera Clovis.

Palabras Clave: Modelo de Entrada Tardío, Modelo de Entrada Temprana y Pre-Clovis.

I. Introduction

The Clovis Barrier, that wall that despite the discoveries made in recent decades, is still standing, however for years cracks have begun to appear in the wall, since new theories and information have generated doubts To a growing number of researchers, on the fact that the Clovis were the first to cross into America and inhabit it, Monte Verde is often cited as the main test to break down the Clovis time barrier dating back to 12,000 BC, but not it is the only argument that can favor acceptance of the late entry model.

Paul Martin in his article on the migration routes to America is convinced that it was towards the end of the last ice age, when groups of hunters from Siberia decided to cross the Bering Bridge, this agrees with the evidence from DNA that has been recovered from some human skeletal remains, indicating a kinship with the Mongoloids (Fiedel 2000). Already in the distant 1614 the possibility that the Asians had been affirmed, when the Englishman Edward Brerewood said something wrong that in reality it had been the Tartars who conquered America, following the line of Martin and Fiedel, we found on the other side of the world, two groups that inhabited Siberia, at the time of the last ice age, we first have the Choukoutian tradition, the oldest dating back to 20,000 years before the present (Fiedel 1996), the Choukoutians, like the Paleo-Americans, have the Mongoloids as members of their family, and it is even believed that these could be their ancestors, however their lithic industry is crude and little worked, so they are not considered as ancestors of the Clovis. The Aurignacians responsible for the colonization and settlement of Australia, Guinea and Tasmania (Fiedel 1996), left the Asian

region of Sahul 25,000 years ago, the possibility that they had arrived by sea to America as they did in Oceania has been ruled out. Only in this case they don't match both DNA and lithic industries, so we actually have no background of the Clovis in Asia, but no ancestors of the Paleoindians.

II. Late Entry Model.

Before continuing, it is a good time to detail the Late Entry Model or as it is causally known as: "Clovis First", 76 are the sites in North America that constitute this model (Grayson and Meltzer 2002), to which we could add those in Central and South America that present points similar to the Clovis as in Belize, but for practical purposes only those from the United States are almost always counted as these are the most studied., Late entry consists of the arrival of groups from the Northeast Asiatic towards the end of the Pleistocene, which crossed the Bridge or Bering Strait towards Alaska, in a period of time where the sea level had considerable drops, being these responsible for colonizing North America and in a period of less than 1000 years they went from New Mexico to the southern cone. An important data that gives more support to the model is the great and rapid mobility that the Clovis groups had on a much larger scale than other prehistoric groups, due to the extent of the sites where their materials have been found (Grayson and Meltzer 2002) In addition to the above, we know that the Clovises travelled, between 300 to 500 km, just to find the raw material they used to make their tools.

According to the previous model, we have Asian groups, they crossed a 1600km long bridge, arriving between 11,500 and 11,290 a.p. to America (Fiedel 2000), extending throughout the southern United States from coast to coast, reaching Clovis points as far away as Belize or Ecuador, and in a period of 1000 years that coincides with the appearance of the Folsom, they would have crossed the entire continent on foot, populating it to the south, due to a kind of blitzkrieg they waged against mammoths in search of food for their population, it sounds too good to be true, although it is unlikely that humans have crossed from Asia to America 30,000 years ago as the most fervent defenders of the Early Entry Model argue, mainly due to 2 factors, Gordon Willey accepts that by exaggerating the human could have reached by 25,000 a.p. due to the type of lithic industries that arose in America, if there had been by 30,000, man would have arrived without tips or knives, but taking into account the evidence from the Yukon, Valsequillo and Tlapacoya sites, he accepts that the Siberian lithic industries of Before 20,000 they already had tips and knives. However, this point reinforces that although no ancestors of the Clovis have been found in Asia, similarities have been found with other types of industries, but that they do not agree chronologically. Geology is the true turning point for me, since the Bering Ice Bridge had two openings, the first around 35,000 BC, when the Mousterian groups that inhabited Siberia still did not have the technology or the clothing to survive any longer. After a season in the frozen tundra, the second opening would have occurred around 22,000 BC, and five thousand years later with a drop in sea level of between 200 to 120 meters, the bridge would be perfectly passable, with a climate similar to the steppe, closing about 12,000 years ago, this second date seems more plausible to me, since by this time there are already groups that inhabit northern Siberia with clear Mongoloid features, there is already the maritime experience of the conquest of Australia, in case of having advanced in boats parallel to the Bering Bridge, there is concordance between the lithic industries, in addition to having sites that demonstrate Pre-Clovis occupations.

Meadowcroft Rockshelter, a site discovered in the 80's of the last century (Fiedel 2000), has radiocarbon dates that give it a supposed age of up to 19,000 years, something that as I pointed out in the previous paragraph could not be possible, in addition to It has Miller-type tips, which are common up to 10,000 BC, so it is discarded as Pre-Clovis, moving to Wisconsin, in Kenosha there is the Chesrow Complex, whose main characteristic is the use of local materials for the elaboration of their artifacts, considered by Addicts to the Late model, as a lithic industry with regional variants contemporary to the Clovis (Fiedel 2000), but which actually has evidence that makes them older, spiky and bifacial in direct association with mammoths and which seems to be a pile of bones piled up of this animal with some knives, as if it were a site of butchering, dating back between 13,450 to 12,200 a.p., Taima-Taima in Venezuela and Valsequillo in Mexico, I do not consider them as Pre-Clovis sites, the first due to the contamination of collagen and soils that were dated by radiocarbon, Fiedel tells out that the

processes of the nearby rivers contaminated the lower strata, creating layers of sediments where antiquities are mixed, while Valsequillo, could not have been inhabited by 27,000 as Lorenzo and Mirambell argue, since there were no proper conditions to have crossed into America in the first place, in addition to not its credibility is helped by the experimental dating of uranium that gave an antiquity of more than 250,000 years, although in its defence, uranium is currently used to know the geological origin of lithic materials.

III. Pre-Clovis.

Finally I present other sites that together with the Chesrow Complex are conclusive evidence of the Clovis were later, the Cactus Hill in Virginia, a settlement that was reoccupied until the Archaic, under a layer corresponding to the Clovis dated by carbon 14 in 10,920 a.p. (Fiedel 2000), a layer with quartzite knives and pentagonal points was found, as well as some pollen particles, which were thrown between 16,670 to 15,070 years before our era, nor Fidel himself, defender of Clovis First, had the arguments to dismiss what was found, pointing out that perhaps given the influx of more Pre-Clovis sites and evidence, it should be considered to delay Clovis for 2000 years, this so that the Topler site in Allendalesouth is not taken into account in the state of Carolina, which features Dalton-type spikes, located one meter below the Clovis strata and predating them by a millennium, and the best for last, that place that makes Clovis addicts tear their clothes, Monte Verde in Chile, a site first excavated, analyzed and studied by Tom Dillehay, who declared that it was a settlement with traces of architecture, which was possibly used seasonally, was abandoned and re occupied, where uncontaminated strata were located and dated, where the footprints of a child were found, among other evidences that when dating gave dates from 12,800 to 11,700 a.p. and one more in 16,000 a.p. I agree with Fidel when saying that the latter turns out to be erratic, this site would indicate that even before the Clovis groups appear, if the delay proposed by Fidel is not considered, the inhabitants of Monte Verde already had a rectangular-shaped settlement of timber materials.

The Early Entry Model, where the human arrived before the Clovis, is in my opinion the correct one, however I do not consider it to be that Early, as I have shown in the previous paragraphs, the conditions for crossing the sea were just a few 17,000 years, to this we must add the evidence from Cactus Hill, which agrees with these dates, if we know that the Clovis were good at moving long distances and some assume that they traveled from North to South America in less than 1000 years, why not assume that other previous groups had the same mobility, if for 17,000 a.p. It began with the crossing and the oldest dates of the Cactus Hill are from 16,670 BC, in less than 400 years they crossed the ice bridge and arrived in the northeast of the United States, in this way the regional variants of the Paleoindian lithic industry such as those of the Chesrow Complex, or the Points of the Dalton type, since it would not have been a single group that crossed, but several, which is reinforced in the linguistic part, due to Greenberg's classification for languages Americans in three types, following this line explains why Pre-Clovis remains appear in Clovis sites, since these would have been reoccupied, with the emergence of the Clovis, in addition to the existence of settlements in South America that predate the Clovis , since the colonization of the continent would have already taken place by that time.

IV. Conclusions.

Both the Dalton tips, the Chesrow, and the Fish Tail, as well as the variants of the Basin of Mexico, are related to the hunting of Megafauna, so that unique character that the Clovis had, having been the only ones to be used to hunt this type of animal is ruled out, however in Mexico, a place that can be used to affirm or deny the models, the evidence found stratigraphically, from the Upper Becerra Strat, agrees with the appearance of the Clovis, so it could be as evidence to affirm the veracity of the Early Entry Model, while the oldest remains, tools, bones that have been dated, such as the humerus from the Peñón III site, do not exceed 10,775 a.p. (González et al. 2003). However, the fact that no antecedents of Clovis have been found in Asia and that if similarities have been found with other lithic industries between both continents, favors the theory that Clovis was a technology that was developed in America, and once it was The first settlers had consolidated, I conclude

by affirming that the wall of the Clovis Barrier, which once seemed to be the most solid at present, is rapidly unravelling, and we are still waiting for new evidence to finish destroying it..

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